
EFFECT OF WORK ENVIRONMENT TO EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN PT DWIGUNATAMA BEKASI, INDONESIA

Nahason Sitohang *¹

*¹ STIE YPBI Jakarta

Abstract:

This research was conducted at PT Dwigunatama Bekasi, Indonesia, with the title "The influence of the work environment on employee performance at PT Dwigunatama Bekasi, Indonesia". The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of the work environment on employee performance at PT Gunatama Bekasi, and how big its influence. The research method used is the field reserch and librarary reserch method with a correlational approach where in the process of collecting data a direct observation is conducted on the company in the form of observation and questionnaire distribution. work environment is anything that is around employees and that can affect employees. Employee Performance is the spirit of work that is the desire and sincerity of someone doing a good job and being disciplined to achieve maximum work performance. The linear regression test is $y = 2.55 + 0.93 X$ and the correlation test is 0.90 which means that the effect is quite strong. Test the coefficient of determination of 81% and the remaining 79.03% is influenced by other factors. The hypothesis test is t arithmetic 14.51 and t table 2.010 means t arithmetic > from t table then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted which means there is a strong enough influence between the work environment on Employee Performance.

Keywords: Work Environment; Employee Performance.

Cite This Article: Nahason Sitohang. (2019). "EFFECT OF WORK ENVIRONMENT TO EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN PT DWIGUNATAMA BEKASI, INDONESIA." *International Journal of Engineering Technologies and Management Research*, 6(10), 37-45. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3533383.

1. Introduction

Background Issues

Human resource management is part of organizational management that focuses on the elements of human resources. The duty of the HRM is to manage the human element well in order to obtain a workforce that is satisfied with his work. In organizations, humans are one of the most important elements in an organization. Without the role of humans even though the various factors needed are available, the organization will not run. Because humans are the driving force and determining the course of an organization. Therefore, the organization should provide positive direction for the achievement of organizational goals. One of the factors that influence the level of success of an organization is the performance of its employees. Employee performance is an action taken by employees in carrying out the work given by the company (Handoko 2001, p.135). Every company always expects its employees to have achievements, because by having employees who excel will provide optimal contributions to the company. In addition, by having employees who excel in the

company can improve the performance of the company. Because companies often face problems regarding human resources. The problem of human resources is a challenge for management because the success of management and others depends on the quality of human resources. If an individual in a company that is his HR can run effectively then the company continues to run effectively. In other words, the survival of a company is determined by the performance of its employees. According to Siagan (2002) that employee performance is influenced by several factors, namely: salary, work environment, organizational culture, leadership and work motivation (motivation), work discipline, job satisfaction, communication and other factors.

Efforts to improve employee performance, including paying attention to work stress. Stress is a condition where a person experiences tension because of the conditions that affect him, these conditions can be obtained from within a person or the environment outside a person. Stress can have a negative impact on psychological and biological conditions for employees. According to Robbin (2002, p.318) stress is a dynamic condition in which an individual is faced with opportunities, limitations or demands in accordance with the expectations of the results he wants to achieve in important and uncertain conditions. According to Sari (2003) examines the influence of sources of work stress on employee performance which shows that individual stress has the most dominant influence on employee performance. On the other hand work stress can be influenced by problems in the company. According to Phillip L. Rice, author of the book *Stress and Health*, a person can be categorized as experiencing work stress if the stressful experience experienced also involves the organization or company where the individual works. Besides stress, another factor that affects employee performance is the work environment. The work environment is anything that is around the workers who can influence themselves in carrying out the tasks assigned, for example cleanliness, music and so on (Nitisemito 1982, p.197). The physical work environment in a company is a working condition to provide a comfortable atmosphere and work situation for employees in achieving the goals desired by a company. Poor working conditions have the potential to cause employees to get sick easily, stress easily, difficulty concentrating and decreased work productivity. Just imagine, if the work space is not comfortable, heat, air circulation is inadequate, the work space is too dense, the work environment is less clean, noisy, of course it will have a major effect on employee work comfort. In achieving the comfort of the workplace, among others, can be done by maintaining physical infrastructure such as cleanliness that is always maintained, adequate lighting, air ventilation, music and comfortable office layout. Because the work environment can create a binding working relationship between the people in the environment (Nitisemito 1982, p.183). The company management should also be able to encourage initiative and creativity. Conditions like these that further create enthusiasm to unite in corporate organizations to achieve company goals by improving employee performance. Research on the influence of employee work environment on employee performance conducted by Nurdyansyah (2009) shows the results of a significant influence between the work environment on employee performance. According to Kusani, (2008) work environment has a significant effect on employee performance. As well as research conducted by Randall Schuller, stress faced by labor is associated with decreased job performance, increased work absenteeism and a tendency to have accidents.

2. References

Definition of the Work

Environment. Employee performance is influenced by many factors and the interest is the amount of composition of compensation given, proper placement, training, security in the future of mutation promotions. In addition to the factors above, there are still other factors that can also affect employee performance in carrying out tasks, namely the work environment. Although this factor is important and has a large influence, many companies have so far paid little attention to this factor. As a matter of melodious music, even though it seems trivial, but it has a huge effect on the effectiveness and efficiency of carrying out tasks. Employees will be able to achieve maximum performance if they have high-achieving motives. The motivating motive that employees need to have must be grown from within themselves and from the work environment. This is because the motive for achievement that is grown from within oneself will form a strength of self and if the work environment situation also supports the achievement of performance will be easier (Mangkunegara 2001, p.68).

According to Anorogo and Widiyanti (1993) the work environment is everything that is around the employee and that can affect him in carrying out the tasks that are charged. The work environment is very influential in the implementation of task completion. Based on the statements above, it can be concluded that the understanding of the work environment is everything that exists around the workers and which can affect themselves in carrying out the tasks assigned (Nitisemito1982, p.159).

3. Types of Work Environment

According Sedarmayanti (2001, p. 21) states that in line large, the type of work environment is divided into two namely:

Physical Work Environment

The physical work environment is all physical conditions that exist around the workplace that can affect employees directly or indirectly. The physical work environment can be divided into two categories namely the environment which is directly related to employees and the intermediary environment or affects the human condition.

Non-Physical Work Environment

Non-physical work environment is all the conditions that occur relating to work relationships, both relationships with superiors and relationships between colleagues, or relations with subordinates. This non-physical environment is also a group of work environments that cannot be ignored.

According to Alex Nitisemito (2000, p.171-173) companies should be able to reflect conditions that support cooperation between superiors, subordinates and those who have the same position status in the company. The conditions that should be created are a family atmosphere, good communication, and self-control.

Suryadi Perwiro Sentoso (2001: 19-21) quoting Prof.'s statement Myon Woo Lee, the originator of the W theory in Human Resource Management, said that the company management should build

a climate and work atmosphere that could arouse a sense of family to achieve common goals. The company management should also be able to encourage initiative and creativity. Conditions like these that further create enthusiasm to unite in corporate organizations to achieve goals.

Factors Affecting the Work Environment

According Soedarmayanti (2001, p. 21) that the factors that can influence the formation of the work environment are as follows:

Lighting Light

Therefore, it should be noted that there is light (light) that is bright but not blinding. The light is less clear, so the work will be slow, many errors, and ultimately lead to less efficient in carrying out the work. Basically, light can be divided into four namely direct light, half direct light, indirect light and indirect halllight.

Air Temperature

Oxygen is a gas that is needed by living things to maintain survival, that is for metabolic processes. The surrounding air is said to be dirty when oxygen levels, in the air have been reduced and have been mixed with gases or odors - odors that are harmful to body health. Feeling cool and fresh at work will help speed up the recovery of the body due to fatigue after work.

Noise

One population that is quite busy with experts to deal with it is noise, the sound that is not desired by the ear. Unwanted, because especially in the long run these sounds can disturb work calm, damage hearing and cause communication errors, even according to research, serious noise can cause death. Because work requires sons concentration, noise should be avoided so that work can be carried out efficiently so that work productivity increases.

Job Safety

In order to maintain the place and condition of the work environment in a safe condition, it is necessary to consider its existence. One effort to maintain security in the workplace, can utilize the Security Officers (SATPAM).

Employee Relations

A pleasant work environment for employees through binding harmonious relationships with superiors, coworkers, and subordinates and supported by adequate facilities and infrastructure in the workplace will have a positive impact on employees, so that employee performance can improve.

According to (Nitisemito 1982, p.159) states that the work environment is measured through indicators as follows:

Work Atmosphere

Every employee always wants a pleasant work atmosphere, a comfortable work atmosphere that includes clear light / lighting, quiet and quiet sounds, security in the workplace. The amount of compensation provided by the company will not affect optimally if the work atmosphere is less conducive. This is in accordance with the opinion of Soedarmayanti (2001, p.46) that lighting,

noise level (quietness) and room temperature as an indicator of the work environment positively affect employee performance.

Relationships with Coworkers

This is meant to be a harmonious relationship with coworkers and with out mutual intrigue between co-workers. One factor that can influence employees to remain in an organization is a harmonious relationship between colleagues. Relationships that can affect employee performance.

Availability of Work Facilities

This means that the equipment is used to support the complete work / up to date. The availability of complete work facilities, although not new is one

Definition

According to Prawirosentono (1999), performance is the work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities in order to achieve the relevant organizational goals legally, not violating the law and in compliance with morals or ethics. Performance is often thought of as achievement of a task, where the term task itself comes from thinking of the activities needed by workers. Because employee performance is an action taken by employees in carrying out work performed by the company (Handoko 1995, p.135). According to Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara (2000, p.67) in his book Human Resources Management, the notion of performance is the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with their responsibilities.

According to Gibson (1997), defining performance as a result of work is related to organizational goals such as quality, efficiency and other work effectiveness criteria. Performance is basically what employees do or don't do. According to Mathis and Jackson (2000), employee performance is what affects how much they give in a company to achieve its goals. Performance can run well if employees get salaries as expected, get training and development, a conducive work environment, get the same treatment, bound employees according to expertise and get career planning assistance, and there is feedback from the company. According to Mangkunegara (2001, p.68) that the characteristics of people who have high performance are as follows: a. Have high personal responsibility. b. Dare to take and bear the risks faced. c. Have realistic goals. d. Having a comprehensive work plan and striving for e. Utilizing concrete feeds back in all work activities that he does.

Factors Influencing Employee

Performance According to Gibson (1997, p.164) states that the factors that influence performance areas follows

Individual Factor Individual Factors Include: ability, skills, family background, work experience, social level and demographics of a person.

Psychological Factors. motivation, work environment and job satisfaction.

Organizational Factors: Organizational structure, job design, leadership and rewards. An employee's performance will be good if: a. Having high expertise. b. Supporting work environment. c. The existence of a decent reward and have a hope for the future, (Prawirosentono,1999).

Factors that affect performance according to Siagian (2002) states that employee performance is influenced by several factors, namely: compensation, work environment, organizational culture, leadership and work motivation, work discipline, job satisfaction, communication and other factors.

According to Sari (quoted from Gomes 1993) stated that Employee performance can be measured through indicators - indicators as follows: a. Quality of work b. Quality of work c. Work creativity d. Work knowledge.

4. Research Methods

This research was conducted at PT Dwigunatama, Bekasi, Indonesia with a number of hypotheses of 500 respondents and with Sugiono's theory, the sample took 10% of the population then the sample was 50 random respondents, the research method used was the field research method by conducting observations directly to the object of research and distributing queasier, besides using the library research method by taking references from scientific books, theses and theses. Data collection from questionnaire responses is then processed by data analysis using simple linear regression analysis, correlation test, coefficient of determination test, and hypnosis test.

5. Discussion Result

Simple Regression

Simple regression analysis of the relationship between the independent variable (X) the work environment and the dependent variable (Y) namely employee performance using a simple regression formula, Sugiyono (2016: 188) as follows: $Y'=a+bX$
Source: Primary Data, processed

$$\begin{array}{l} n = 50 \qquad \qquad \qquad \sum X = 2102 \qquad \qquad \qquad \sum Y = 2094 \\ \sum X^2 = 88998 \qquad \qquad \sum Y^2 = 88382 \qquad \qquad \sum XY = 88621 \end{array}$$

$$a = \frac{(\sum Y)(\sum X^2) - (\sum X)(\sum XY)}{n \cdot \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2} = \frac{(2094)(88998) - (2102)(88621)}{50 \cdot 88998 - (2102)^2} = \frac{80470}{31496} = 2,55$$

$$b = \frac{n \sum XY - \sum X \cdot \sum Y}{n \cdot \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2} = \frac{50 \cdot 88621 - 2102 \cdot 2094}{50 \cdot 88998 - (2102)^2} = 0,93$$

From this calculation can be interpreted if there is a change in the variable X by 1 point, the value of the variable Y will increase to 2.5 points.

Then the regression equation is $Y = 2.55 + 0.93 X$

Simple Correlation Coefficient Analysis

Simple Correlation Analysis is used to measure the magnitude of the effect work environment on employee performance to find out the magnitude The Correlation Coefficient, the following calculations are made:

$$\begin{aligned}
 n &= 50 & \sum X &= 2102 & \sum Y &= 2094 \\
 \sum X^2 &= 88998 & \sum Y^2 &= 88382 & \sum XY &= 88621 \\
 r_{xy} &= \frac{n \sum X_i Y_i - (\sum X_i)(\sum Y_i)}{\sqrt{\{n \sum X_i^2 - (\sum X_i)^2\} \{n \sum Y_i^2 - (\sum Y_i)^2\}}} \\
 &= \frac{50 \cdot 88621 - (2102)(2094)}{\sqrt{\{50 \cdot 88998 - (2102)^2\} \{50 \cdot 88382 - (2094)^2\}}} \\
 &= \frac{4431050 - 4401588}{\sqrt{4449900 - 4418404} \sqrt{4419100 - 4384836}} = \frac{29462}{\sqrt{31496 \cdot 34264}} = 0,90
 \end{aligned}$$

From the results of the correlation coefficient above the correlation value 0.90 which means work environment has a very strong influence on employee performance.

Determination Coefficient Analysis (KD)

To find out how much the work environment on employee performance can use the determination coefficient formula (KD) as follows: $KD = r^2 \times 100\% = 0,90^2 \times 100\% = 0,81 \times 100\% = 81\%$

From the results of the coefficient of determination above which means the work environment affects the performance of employees 81% and the remaining 19%

$$by = \frac{0,90 \sqrt{50-2}}{\sqrt{1-0,90^2}} = \frac{0,90 \sqrt{48}}{\sqrt{0,19}} = \frac{6,24}{0,43} = 14,51$$

then obtained a tcount of 14.51

2. Determine the a and t tables $a = 5\% = 0,05\%$

$dk = n - 2 = 50 - 2 = 48$ with a significant level of 5%, 2,010 were obtained

Test incriteria Furthermore, it is compared with Tcount from the calculation result with Ttable under the condition: If T arithmetic > T table then Ha is accepted and H0

If Tcount < Ttable then Ha is accepted and H0

Ha = There is a significant relationship between variable X and Y

From the above hypothesis test it can be concluded that Tcount > Ttable is $14.51 > 2.010$, Ha is accepted and H0. It can be concluded that there is a significant influence between the work environment (variable X) and employee performance (variable Y)

6. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion by the author about "The influence of the work environment on the performance of employees of PT Dwigunatama Bekasi Indonesia,". Then the writer can conclude:

- 1) From the calculation of a simple regression equation obtained regression = $\hat{Y} = 2.55 + 0.93X$. This means that any change in work environment of 1 will be able to affect employee performance by 0.93. So, the work environment has an effect of 0.93 on the performance of employees of PT. Dwigunatama Bekasi
- 2) From the simple correlation calculation results above, it can be concluded that the correlation coefficient $r_{xy} = 0.90$, meaning that there is a very strong influence between work environment variables and employee performance.
- 3) Based on the above calculation it can be seen from the coefficient of determination (KD) of 81%. Then the influence of the work environment on employee performance by 81%. It also states that 19% is influenced by other factors.
- 4) From the results of hypothesis testing obtained t count $14.51 > t_{table} 0.2787$, means H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected, so it can be concluded that there is a significant influence between the work environment on employee performance at PTDwigunatamaBekasi Indonesia.

7. Suggestion

Based on the research results obtained above, the author can provide suggestions to PT Dwigunatama Bekasi as follows:

- 1) PT. Dwigunatama should the work environment must always be maintained and cared for so that employees will still feel comfortable to continue to work well.
- 2) PT. Dwigunatama should give awards or rewards to employees who are acting so that employees get enthusiasm or work motivation will continue to increase which will affect the quality of work of their employees.
- 3) PT. Dwigunatama should be more active in conducting training on employee performance to improve the quality of services provided to customers, so that customers will continue to use the company's services.

References

- [1] Resty Fawzia. 2014. "The Effect of Motivation, Communication and Work Environment on the Performance of the Faculty of Economics and Business Employees". Thesis. Surakarta: Faculty of Economics and Business, Muhammadiyah University, Surakarta.
- [2] Amri, Sirlil. 2013. "The Relationship Between Work Motivation and Employee Performance in the Production Section of PT. Sari Color Original Unit II Boyolali ". Thesis. Surakarta: Faculty of Psychology, Muhammadiyah University Surakarta. Analysis.
- [3] Lucky Wulan. 2011. "Analysis of the Effect of Work Motivation and Work Environment on Employee Performance (Study at the Department of Industry and Trade Semarang City)". Thesis. Semarang: Faculty of Economics, Diponegoro University